

MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PEDIATRIC OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNEA: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Obstructive Sleep apnea (OSA) affects approximately 1%-5% of children. There is an increase in the risk of cardiac arrhythmias, stroke, cardiovascular disease, hypertension, pulmonary hypertension, and altered immune function due to this disorder, which profoundly affects various body systems. Overnight polysomnograms are increasingly used to diagnose conditions and implement therapy more quickly at a lower cost. Various surgical and non-surgical interventions are available for treating pediatric OSA. This review will focus on adenotonsillectomy and positive airway pressure therapy for pediatric OSA. Furthermore, we also discussed non-surgical and surgical interventions for managing pediatric OSA. Additionally, we discussed current research efforts exploring newer diagnostic techniques and experimental treatment modalities. Healthcare professionals can effectively address the challenges of pediatric OSA with advancements in diagnostic tools and treatment approaches.

Keywords: Obstructive sleep apnea, Pediatric population, surgical interventions, non-surgical interventions

1. INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a significant physiological need and a reversible state of partial unresponsiveness or detachment from the environment. It is essential to a child's well-being, growth, and day-to-day functioning [1, 2]. The temperature of the body drops, sleep glucose metabolism increases, uric acid, sodium, and potassium are excreted, and cortisol and TSH are secreted at lower levels during sleep [3]. Sleep disorders include insomnia, parasomnias, narcolepsy, breathing, circadian rhythm, and sleep-related movement disorders. Apnea is the termination of airflow for at least 10 seconds, escorted by a decline in oxygen saturation. In contrast, sleep apnea is the intermittent stopping of airflow in the mouth and nose during sleep [4, 5]. Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) [6] was first described in detail by Charles Dickens nearly 150 years before the term was used. William Osler first identified a sleep-related breathing problem, or obstructive sleep apnea syndrome, in 1918. The phrase "complex sleep apnea syndrome" has been widely used recently. One of children's most common sleep problems is obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) [7]. Obstructive sleep apnea is a chronic disorder characterized by periods of upper airway collapse and leading to decreased airflow during sleep. Because of this, you'll

wake up periodically at night and have difficulty getting back to sleep [8]. Untreated OSA in children can have serious short- and long-term effects. Pediatric OSA adversely affects the quality of life [9]. Intensely, it prompts cognitive dysfunction and daytime sleepiness [10]. It has also been linked to cardiovascular and neurobehavioral dysfunction [11]. OSA affect 1 to 2% of all children; However, OSA diagnosis typically occurs 3.3 years after significant symptoms first appear in children [12]. Between 1980 and 2008, the prevalence of childhood obesity tripled, with an estimated 60% of obese children and adolescents experiencing OSA [13, 14]. There is a connection between child obesity and OSA; different racial/ethnic groups and socioeconomic backgrounds are associated with different risks for pediatric OSA [14]. Obesity, impaired neuromotor tone, adenotonsillar hypertrophy, and a high loop gain all play a role in the pathophysiology of pediatric OSA [15, 16]. Children with genetic disorders like craniofacial abnormalities, Down syndrome, and neuromuscular conditions are also at an increased risk of developing OSA [17]. Caregiver reports of snoring or breathing difficulties during sleep, hyperactivity, and excessive daytime drowsiness are common among children with OSA [18]. Children with OSA are at increased risk for neurocognitive issues, behavioural issues, poor academic performance, and cardiovascular risks, which can result in a substantial healthcare burden if the condition is left untreated [17, 18]. The severity of OSA is measured by the polysomnographic (PSG-derived) obstructive apnea and hypopnea index (AHI) [19, 20]. Overnight polysomnography (PSG) in a sleep lab is used to diagnose OSA [20]. Children with mild obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) have an apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) of 1 to 5. Patients with moderate OSA exhibit an AHI of 5 to 10 events per hour, while those with severe OSA exhibit an AHI of 10 or more per hour [21, 22]. This review discusses treatment options, including positive airway pressure and adenotonsillectomy. Non-surgical and surgical interventions and emerging treatments, including drug-induced sleep endoscopy and hypoglossal nerve stimulation, are also discussed. The review provides insights into efficacy, limitations, and ongoing research in pediatric OSA management.

2. HISTORY OF SLEEP APNEA

In the mid-1850s, periodic breathing in sleep was first reported; by the 1870s, British doctors had documented several obstructed apneas cases, which they described as "during sleep, individuals experiencing glottic obstruction may exhibit cyanosis and futile contractions of the inspiratory and expiratory muscles in an attempt to overcome the obstruction" [23]. In the latter half of the 19th century, there were several documented cases of individuals experiencing morbid obesity and excessive daytime drowsiness [24]. These cases led to the condition being named "Pickwickian syndrome," inspired by the character Fat Boy Joe from Charles Dickens's *Pickwick Papers*, published in 1837 [25]. During the transition into the 20th century, British physiologists Douglas, Mabel Fitzgerald and John Scott Haldane observed periodic breathing in healthy individuals sleeping at high altitudes with low oxygen levels [26]. In the early to mid-19th century, British physician Hunter and Irish physicians Stokes and Cheyne reported periodic breathing in

patients with heart failure [23, 27-30]. Simulating cyclic hypoxia in mice allowed researchers to observe the gradual onset of daytime hypertension in the early 1990s, generating interest in studying sleep apnea's long-term cardiovascular effects [31, 32]. Recent studies have revealed that patients with sleep apnea exhibit increased genioglossus EMG activity while awake and during non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that these patients maintain upper airway patency while awake through compensatory and amplified EMG activity of their airway dilator muscles [33-34]. The Wisconsin Sleep Cohort study utilized in-lab sleep and breathing investigations and found a significant prevalence of sleep-disordered breathing in a middle-aged, nonclinical population [35]. These findings highlighted the substantial and underdiagnosed public health impact of sleep-disordered breathing [36]. Since the mid-1990s, numerous scientific, clinical, and population-level studies have focused on examining this persistent issue's incidence, pathogenesis, and management. Researchers and clinicians from various disciplines have dedicated their efforts to studying sleep apnea. Despite being a significant clinical condition, sleep apnea has prompted the establishment of several commercial ventures aimed at its detection and treatment, including the proliferation of sleep medicine clinics across the Western world, with a strong emphasis on sleep apnea treatment. Lastly, the high incidence of sleep apnea as a sleep-specific condition with potential daytime implications has greatly accelerated the advancement of sleep medicine.

3. EPIDEMIOLOGY OF OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNEA

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) in children has gained significant recognition as a potential cause of severe health complications only in recent decades [37]. OSA is characterized by partial or complete upper airway obstruction during sleep, leading to disrupted breathing patterns. Before puberty, the incidence of OSA is similar in boys and girls [38]. However, as children reach puberty, the prevalence of OSA increases among boys, leading to a notable disparity between the genders [39]. Researchers have observed that the incidence of OSA peaks twice a year, with the initial spike followed in children aged 2 to 8 with enlarged adenoids or tonsils [40]. The second peak coincides with the onset of puberty and weight gain, further affecting boys more than girls [41]. Several factors contribute to the growing prevalence of OSA in children. Urbanization and dietary transitions have led to changes in lifestyle and eating habits, resulting in an increased risk of obesity and metabolic syndrome [42]. These conditions are known to be associated with the development of OSA. Consequently, OSA is becoming a more widely recognized disease, particularly in predominantly Asian Indian children, affecting approximately 2-5% of this population [43].

4. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF SLEEP APNEA

The pharynx, a very complex structure, is frequently the source of congestion in the upper airway. The pharyngeal muscles help with swallowing, vocalization, and preserving pharyngeal patency during inspiration. Each pharyngeal muscle serves a different

purpose when the others are contracted or in a particular posture [44, 45]. During inspiration, the luminal area of the pharynx reflects the equilibrium between the constriction of the pharynx due to retropharyngeal negative suction pressure and the dilation of the pharyngeal muscles [46]. The transmural pressure has a role in how the relaxed pharynx behaves. When the transmural pressure is raised, the pharynx remains open, whereas when it is lowered, the pharynx closes [47]. The transmural closure pressure is when the pharyngeal area reaches a complete decline or reduction to zero [48]. As the pharynx luminal area diminishes, it becomes more vulnerable to collapse. Surface adhesive forces, jaw opening, neck flexion, and gravity are static factors that narrow the pharyngeal airway [49]. In contrast, tracheal tug caused by increased neck extension and lung volume are static factors that dilate the pharynx [50]. Moreover, dynamic factors such as increased nasal resistance, increased dynamic compliance of the pharynx, and the Bernoulli effect can also promote pharyngeal narrowing [51].

Figure 1: Pathophysiology of Obstructive sleep apnea

The central nervous system continuously activates the pharyngeal muscles to keep the pharynx open in healthy, awake humans. The patency of the upper airway is often compromised by a decrease in this activation during sleep [52]. Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is caused by decreased brain activity and pharyngeal anatomic anomalies such as an oversized tongue, a low-hanging palate, or extra posterior pharyngeal tissue. Neural output to the pharyngeal muscles is increased by hypercapnia and hypoxia and proprioceptive feedback from thoracic and upper airway receptors [53,54]. Sleep deprivation, alcohol, anaesthesia, and sedative-hypnotics reduce pharyngeal muscle activation. During sleep, such chemical feedback is dampened, and proprioceptive feedback is eliminated [55, 56].

Pharyngeal constriction can occur on a periodic or irregular basis. Combined with periods of normal airflow are apneas, hypopneas, or both, caused by the periodic blockage. Constantly rising airflow resistance, with or without desaturation, characterizes nonperiodic blockage [57]. Upper airway resistance syndrome refers to the symptoms of sleep disturbance and daytime sleepiness caused by a persistent increase in airway resistance. 32 The velopharynx, oropharynx, and hypopharynx can all become constricted in OSA patients. The velopharynx is the most common location of obstruction [58,59]. Ventilation is eliminated or significantly reduced at complete closure or significant upper airway constriction; hypercarbia and hypoxia can flourish [60]. Respiratory effort rises in reaction to these chemo stimuli, leading to arousal. This results in increased pharyngeal dilator muscle activation and the subsequent clearance of the impediment in the upper airway. This process can occur repeatedly at night, resulting in fragmented sleep and adrenergic spikes due to hypoxia and hypercarbia, as shown in Figure. 1.

5. CLINICAL SIGNS OF SLEEP APNEA

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a common sleep condition characterized by the complete or partial blocking of the upper airway repeatedly during the night [61]. Various clinical indications and symptoms are essential for diagnosing and treating this disease. Constant snoring is a classic symptom of OSA [62,63]. People with OSA generally snore loudly and continuously throughout the night. During these bouts of snoring, breathing stops (apneas) occur regularly [61]. These pauses in breathing might cause the person to gasp or choke as they try to regain air. These disruptions might cause sleep to become fragmented and of worse quality than usual [64]. There are other clinical indications of OSA besides snoring and breathing interruptions. During sleep, some people's legs may remain somewhat constant or non-dynamic [65]. Breathing might be difficult when the tonsils are enlarged because they block the airway [61, 66]. During apnea attacks, you can see paradoxical chest movement, in which your chest and belly move in opposite directions while you breathe [65]. OSA effects are not limited to those experienced at night; they can also influence during the day. People with OSA sometimes experience extreme daytime tiredness despite obtaining the recommended amount of sleep each night [61].

Parasomnias may also coexist with insomnia, including sleepwalking or having terrifying dreams while you sleep [67]. The consequences of OSA are multiplied in children. Growth retardation and disruptive classroom conduct are common symptoms [68]. Children who suffer from OSA often have trouble sleeping and poor sleep quality, which can negatively affect their academic performance and general health [61, 68]. OSA is also linked to bedwetting in children [68, 69]. At the same time, drowsiness throughout the day and interrupted breathing during sleep are common symptoms of OSA in adults [70]. A thorough medical assessment is necessary for the diagnosis and treatment of OSA. Modifications in living, CPAP therapy, oral appliances, and even surgery are all potential treatments for sleep apnea. Treating OSA is crucial for promoting health and quality of life by enhancing sleep, decreasing daytime symptoms, and decreasing snoring.

Figure 2: Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome clinical symptoms

6. METHODS FOR SLEEP APNEA DIAGNOSIS

6.1 History and Physical Examination

History, clinical suspicion, and physical evidence confirm or rule out obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS). The history and physical examination should include questions about the patient's nightly and daytime symptoms and any neurobehavioral impairments, behavioural issues, drowsiness, failure to grow, or systemic hypertension that may be related to OSAS [71,72]. The prevalence of nighttime snoring is the best predictor of OSA [73,74]. Pay close attention to the size and placement of the tonsils, the existence of allergic rhinitis or any other disease likely to enhance nasal airflow resistance, and the size and placement of the mandible (micrognathia and retrognathia, respectively) [75]. A comprehensive assessment of the upper airway, from the nose to the oropharynx, involves a series of sequential steps. This thorough physical examination can assist in identifying any potential anatomical constriction. 1) It's essential to check for strayed septums, enlarged inferior turbinates, collapsed nasal valves during inspiration, and asymmetry of the nasal auricle. 2) The uvula location of the Tongue can be determined by observing the oropharynx. 3) The tonsils size to the airway should be evaluated. 4) Signs of a tiny jaw or atypical maxilla-mandibular development include a high and narrow hard palate, overlapping incisors, a crossbite, and an overjet of at least 2 millimetres [76]. It is impossible to distinguish between regular snorers and those with obstructive sleep apnea based only on a patient's clinical history and physical examination. Since the clinical history has a 65% PPV and the physical exam has a 45% PPV, the American Academy of Pediatrics recommends objective testing with overnight polysomnography [77].

6.2 Neck Circumference

Neck circumference and fatty infiltration are further diagnostic criteria for OSA [78]. Signs of sleep-disordered breathing include an adenoid face and using lips to breathe while awake. Retrognathia, micrognathia, and midfacial hypoplasia can all be diagnosed using a lateral facial profile examination [79]. A blaring second pulmonary heart sound may indicate pulmonary hypertension in patients with severe OSAS [78]. Children with OSAS often have growth impairments and developmental delays; thus, it is crucial to monitor their progress.

6.3 Sedation-Assisted Endoscopy

Using a specialized diagnostic procedure, a sedation-assisted endoscopy determines the location of the highest airway pressure. Usually, it is used to treat children with severe airway abnormalities and congenital craniofacial defects. It allows a thorough airway examination using sedation and an endoscope [86]. Generally, this treatment is reserved for children with congenital craniofacial and airway anomalies [83,87]. A child with sleep-disordered breathing undergoes drug-induced sleep endoscopy (DISE) to observe the upper airway while sedation is administered. A DISE study of children with complex airway disorders [88] found the technique useful for identifying obstruction sites and

guiding surgical decisions. Sedation endoscopy allowed for assessing the upper airway during natural sleep, identifying obstruction sites and facilitating treatment planning.

6.4 X-Ray of Paranasal Sinuses

Diagnostic X-rays of the sinuses and neck can reveal sinusitis and adenoid hypertrophy in the paranasal sinuses [80]. Sinusitis consists of inflamed or infected paranasal sinuses [81], whereas adenoid hypertrophy occurs when the adenoid tissue is enlarged in the upper airway [82]. As a result, air-fluid levels, mucosal thickening, sinus opacification, and sinus wall abnormalities may be detected as signs of sinus inflammation [83]. The size and location of the adenoids to the nasopharynx can be determined with X-ray imaging. An increased density or opacity of soft tissue in the nasopharynx is often a sign of adenoid hypertrophy [84]. In the case of obstructive sleep apnea, X-ray imaging cannot provide detailed information about the severity or location of abnormal airway structures. Further imaging modalities such as MRI and CT may be necessary to obtain more detailed information about anatomical structures.

6.5 Polysomnography

Polysomnography (PSG) serves as the confirmatory tool. Polysomnography (PSG) includes electroencephalogram (EEG) leads, electromyogram (EMG), electrooculogram (EOG), oral thermistor/nasal pressure, pulse oximetry, electrocardiogram (ECG), abdominal and chest excursion belts, oesophageal manometry, plethysmography, limb leads, end-tidal or transcutaneous carbon dioxide (CO₂), and audio/videotaping. Sleep architecture, breathing events (hypopneas, apneas, respiratory effort-related arousals flow restriction), REM sleep, desaturation, respiratory effort, and autonomic alterations may all be assessed with the data supplied by these measures [89]. Audio and video recordings, a home monitoring device, questionnaires, nightly pulse oximetry, sleep endoscopy, and tracheal sound signals are among other diagnostic tools that have been developed. Future alternatives to PSG [90] may include urine biomarkers, polygraphy, and rhinomanometry, all of which have good diagnostic test accuracy. In-laboratory polysomnography (grade A) is recommended by the American Academy of Pediatrics for children who snore frequently (3 nights/week) and who also complain of any of the following: gasping or snorting, difficulty breathing while sleeping, observed apneas, unusual sleep position, nocturnal secondary enuresis, cyanosis, daytime sleepiness, headache upon awakening, hyperactivity/attention, and learning problems [91]. Polysomnography is used to diagnose OSA in children by recording various parameters during sleep. These include the child's brain waves (electroencephalogram; frontal, bilateral central, occipital EEG), eye movements (EOG, electrooculogram); leg and chin electromyogram; airflow signals (nasal cannula pressure transducer and oronasal thermal airflow sensor) and dual thoracoabdominal respiratory effort signals [92]. Infants, children, and adults all have significantly diverse sleep patterns that must be considered when evaluating sleep tests.

6.5.1 Levels of Testing

To diagnose OSA, four distinct levels might be used. A sleep technologist oversees a Level I polysomnogram, which measures at least seven factors (including electrooculography, electromyography of the chin, electroencephalography, airflow, oxygen saturations, respiratory effort, and electrocardiography). Similar to Level I, Level II requires a minimum of seven parameters but does not need the presence of a sleep technician. Four parameters are required for Level III (electrocardiogram/pulse oximeter, oxygen saturation monitor, respiratory effort monitor, and airflow monitor) to monitor without a sleep technician. Finally, level IV research requires at least three channels (airflow, actigraphy, oxygen desaturation, and peripheral arterial tone). Level IV sleep monitoring can be performed with or without a sleep technologist present [91,93-95].

Table 1: Sleep apnea diagnosis

Diagnostic Tool/Method	Description	Limitations	Ref.
Clinical History and Examination	Involves questioning the patient about symptoms and physical examination of the upper airway, tonsil size, nasal anatomy, and facial features.	Cannot distinguish between regular snorers and those with OSA based solely on the clinical history and physical examination.	[71,72]
Neck Circumference	The neck circumference measurement can be an additional diagnostic criterion for OSAS.	Neck circumference alone cannot provide a definitive diagnosis of OSA and should be used with other diagnostic tools.	[78,79]
X-ray of Paranasal Sinuses	X-ray imaging of the paranasal sinuses and the side of the neck to diagnose sinusitis and adenoid hypertrophy.	X-ray imaging may not provide detailed information about the severity or precise location of airway abnormalities associated with OSAS.	[80,83]
Sedation-Assisted Endoscopy	A method was used on children with congenital craniofacial anomalies and severe airway abnormalities to pinpoint the location of the highest airway pressure.	This method only applies to a specific population (children with congenital craniofacial anomalies) and is not a routine diagnostic tool for OSAS.	[86,88]
Polysomnography (PSG)	Considered the confirmatory tool for diagnosing OSAS, involving multiple measures to assess sleep architecture, breathing events, and autonomic alterations.	Requires specialized facilities and trained personnel and can be expensive. It may not be readily available in all healthcare settings.	[89-91]
Level I Polysomnogram	Comprehensive sleep study involving various physiological parameters to assess sleep architecture, breathing events, and autonomic alterations.	Requires the presence of a sleep technologist and may not be easily accessible or feasible for all patients due to cost and availability.	[91]
Level II Polysomnogram	Similar to Level I polysomnography, it measures	Level II polysomnography may require specialized equipment	[93,94]

	the same parameters but does not require the presence of a sleep technologist.	and may not be as widely available as other diagnostic methods.	
Level III Polysomnogram	Involves monitoring specific parameters without a sleep technologist, providing limited information compared to higher-level polysomnography.	Provides limited information compared to Level I or Level II polysomnography.	[91,93]
Level IV Polysomnogram	Sleep monitoring, with a minimum of three channels, can be performed with or without a sleep technologist present.	Provides limited information compared to higher-level polysomnography and may not be as accurate or comprehensive in diagnosing OSAS.	[95]
Sleep Testing in Different Ages	Different sleep tests need to consider age-related differences for accurate evaluation.	Sleep tests should be adapted and validated for different age groups to ensure accurate diagnosis and interpretation of results.	[96]
Other Diagnostic Tools	Audio and video recordings, home monitoring devices, questionnaires, and measurements are included.	Alternative diagnostic tools may have good diagnostic test accuracy, but their availability, reliability, and standardization may vary.	[97,98]

7. CONSEQUENCES AND COMPLICATIONS OF PEDIATRIC OSA

7.1 Hypertension

Around 40% of people with OSA also have hypertension [99]. Men in their middle 30s with hypertension are disproportionately affected by OSA. According to three recent significant clinical trials, it was found that individuals with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) had a 1.5- to 3-fold higher risk of developing hypertension [100-101]. Similarly, the Wisconsin Sleep Cohort study revealed a greater occurrence of hypertension among patients with an apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) of 30 or higher. [102].

7.2 Pulmonary disorders

7.2.1 Pulmonary hypertension

In cases where daytime hypoxia or coexisting pulmonary disease is not present, obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) can lead to mild pulmonary hypertension but typically does not advance to clinical right-heart failure [103-105]. Weitzenblum et al. [106] found that about 15% of OSA patients had abnormally high pulmonary artery pressure at rest.

7.2.2 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

It is also possible for OSA to coexist with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Although around 10% of OSA patients also have COPD, the nocturnal oxygen desaturation that typically occurs is predominantly caused by hypoventilation associated with REM sleep rather than apneas [107]. Nighttime desaturation can occur due to two

potential reasons: sleep-related ventilation and perfusion mismatch and reduced capacity of functional residual. Patients with hypercapnic COPD may more likely experience obstructive apneas because of a constricted pharynx while awake [107,108]. The severity of nocturnal desaturation was higher in patients with a combination of the two diseases [109], even though Sanders et al. [110] reported no clear suggestion between OSA and mild COPD.

7.3 Cardiac disorder

7.3.1 ischemic heart disease

Coronary artery disease patients with OSA may be at increased risk for cardiac ischemia due to nighttime hypoxemia and increased adrenergic tone caused by obstructive apneas-hypopneas [111]. Myocardial infarction danger is highest at the lowest oxygen levels when the heart rate and blood pressure are elevated. Patients with sleep apnea have also been shown to have a diminished ability for fibrinolysis, which may further elevate their risk for coronary occlusion [112]. Population studies have shown that persons who snore chronically are at a higher risk of developing angina. Peker et al. [113] found that 37% of patients with OSA originally reported cardiovascular disease, compared to just 7% of patients without OSA, in a cohort of middle-aged people sent to a sleep clinic for OSA examination. During a median follow-up period of 7 years, it was observed that 57% of individuals with inadequately controlled obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) developed new cardiovascular disease, whereas only 7% of patients with well-managed OSA experienced the same outcome. Results showed that OSA plays a significant role in the aetiology of coronary artery disease.

7.3.2 Arrhythmias

Arrhythmias of the heart are more common in patients with OSA. Fifty-eight percent of OSA patients were found to have arrhythmias by Hoffstein and Mateika [114]. Arrhythmia patients typically present with more severe cases of sleep apnea and nocturnal hypoxemia [115]. According to Flemons et al. [116], oxygen desaturation to 60% or below and an AHI of at least ten occurrences per hour are arrhythmogenic. During the apneic period of sleep apnea, bradycardia is the most prevalent irregular rhythm, followed by tachycardia when the apnea ends. Other arrhythmias can include premature ventricular contractions, atrial tachycardia, second-degree heart block, sinus arrest, atrial flutter, paroxysmal atrial fibrillation, and nonsustained ventricular tachycardia.

7.3.3 Congestive heart failure

In patients with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) and congestive heart failure, continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy results in heightened sensitivity of baroreflex receptors. This improvement enhances the brain's regulation of heart rate, leading to a reduction in heart rate by resetting the working point of the baroreceptors. As a result, blood pressure is lowered [117]. CPAP treatment also improves neural control of heart rate and reduces heart rate by lowering the patient's blood pressure. By reducing OSA, CPAP prevents blood pressure drops after a normal apnea episode [118]. When these

factors are added together, cardiac afterload decreases, which may enhance cardiac performance.

7.4 Cerebrovascular disease

Apneas cause fluctuations in cerebral perfusion, which may limit blood flow to parts of the brain with marginal or poor circulation [119]. Individuals who snore have an odds ratio of 3.2 for stroke. In contrast, those who snore and have observed apneas, excessive daytime drowsiness, or obesity have an odds ratio of 8 [120, 121]. Patients with a history of stroke are also at a higher risk of developing OSA.

7.5 Neurocognitive function

Daytime sleepiness, sadness, and cognition deficits are common symptoms of classic sleep apnea [122]. Recent research from the Wisconsin Sleep Cohort has shown that middle-aged people with untreated sleep apnea had a worse psychomotor performance [123]. Neurocognitive performance was shown to be decreased at an AHI of 15 occurrences per hour or higher, as reported by Kim et al. [124], which is comparable to the impact of providing a sedative-hypnotic at a dosage of around 50%.

Figure 2: Consequences of obstructive pulmonary disease

8. TREATMENT OF OSA

Figure 3: Overview of treatments steps for OSA

8.1 Surgical Treatment Method

8.1.1 Adenotonsillectomy

The tonsil is removed during a tonsillectomy, a surgical technique that dissects the peritonsillar area between the capsule and muscle wall. This operation is called an adenotonsillectomy. Adenotonsillectomy treats a child with OSAS and adenotonsillar hypertrophy [125]. When treating pediatric OSA, adenotonsillectomy is typically the primary treatment option. Eliminating tonsils and adenoids enhances the dimensions of the upper airway, reducing the likelihood of collapse [126]. A significant randomized controlled trial investigating the treatment of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) treatment through adenotonsillectomy made noteworthy findings. The trial revealed that adenotonsillectomy led to apnea resolution in 79% of the participants, while only 46% of those who underwent a period of watchful waiting experienced the same outcome [127].

However, no significant differences were observed in primary outcomes, such as attention and executive function measures, between the two groups. Nevertheless, moderate-quality data indicated that adenotonsillectomy improved quality of life, sleep apnea symptoms, and behavioural outcomes [128].

Adenotonsillectomy has risks, although the procedure successfully treats pediatric OSA. Most patients require supplementary oxygen after surgery due to chronic nocturnal desaturations caused by respiratory impairment. About 9.4% of patients have this, but it goes away throughout the healing process [129]. The incidence rates of primary haemorrhage (within 24h) and secondary haemorrhage (after 24 hours after surgery) are 2.4 and 2.6%, respectively [130]. Post-operative discomfort and dehydration from poor fluid intake are two additional potential problems. Children younger than 3 years, cardiac complications, neuromuscular disorders, severe OSA, craniofacial anomalies, obesity, and concurrent respiratory infections are identified risk factors for postoperative complications [127]. For children whose clinical examination does not align with the severity of their disease regarding adenoid or tonsil enlargement, it is advisable to undergo a more thorough and comprehensive assessment of the upper airway using polysomnography (PSG). For instance, some children have adenotonsillar hypertrophy but seldom experience sleep apnea episodes, and some children experience sleep apnea episodes often but do not have adenotonsillar hypertrophy. It's also important to think about other systemic disorders that might have a role in causing OSA. Children with OSA who have tiny tonsils and those with recurrent OSA may benefit greatly from airway reconstruction and drug-induced sleep endoscopy (DISE) by imaging [131]. These patients may also benefit greatly from multidisciplinary consulting. We have gained insights into the benefits, limitations, and considerations of adenotonsillectomy for pediatric OSA. Adenotonsillectomy is an effective primary treatment option for pediatric OSA. Further research could focus on long-term outcomes, surgical refinements, and personalized approaches to enhance treatment efficacy and minimize risks.

8.2 Non-invasive intervention

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) may continue despite adenotonsillectomy in high-risk groups [132]. Non-invasive positive airway pressure (PAP) therapy proves to be an effective treatment for children who have residual obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) or for those who are not suitable candidates for adenotonsillectomy. A nasal mask or other interface provides pressurized air from a machine in this treatment. Sleep apnea is treated by delivering pressurized air to the upper airway [133]. CPAP and BPAP, or bilevel positive airway pressure, are popular forms of PAP used on children. Auto-adjusting continuous positive airway pressure (AutoPAP) devices utilize proprietary software to monitor the patient's breathing actively. This software provides real-time feedback to the machine, enabling it to adjust the pressure settings dynamically. This adaptive feature ensures the device delivers adequate pressure to address apneas during sleep [134] effectively. This mode of CPAP is becoming increasingly prescribed, especially in older children. Nasal congestion, epistaxis, and dry mouth are potential complications of

continuous positive airway pressure treatment. Despite the effectiveness of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) in treating obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), the challenge of ensuring patient adherence to therapy remains a significant barrier [135, 136]. Strong family support, maternal education, and caregiver self-efficacy have all been linked to increased PAP use in children with OSA [137,138]. Strategies for improving CPAP adherence include multidisciplinary support and behavioural therapy.

At least once a year after starting (Non-invasive ventilation) NIV, a follow-up sleep study and assessment of clinical parameters, including compliance and breathing effect, are recommended. When the therapy efficacy declines, the child's body mass index (BMI) z-score changes, or other medications are added, it is important to reevaluate the patient with PSG [139]. CPAP therapy can cause side effects, such as nose discomfort, skin damage, and eye irritation. Using PAP for an extended time increases the risk of midface hypoplasia in younger children [140]. Therefore, monitoring maxillofacial development regularly is advised [139,140, 141]. Children have a lower rate of treatment compliance with NIV than adults; hence there is less data on the effectiveness of NIV in pediatric settings. Previous research has found that NIV therapy is only adhered to between 30 and 60% of the time while sleeping, lasting only 3.3 to 5.3 hours [142-145]. The PAP device provides an objective method for measuring compliance by uploading data from a smart card or modem to a remote server. The adherence to non-invasive ventilation (NIV) usage during the initial phase or within the first month of treatment often indicates the treatment's long-term viability. This underscores the importance of timely suctioning as a critical factor in sustaining effective NIV therapy [146, 147]. Research investigating the factors impeding compliance with positive airway pressure (PAP) therapy has indicated that gender, age, family economic status, maternal education, level of family support, asthma, caregiver self-efficacy, and the provision of warming and humidification are all associated with adherence to PAP treatment.

8.3 Other non-surgical treatment modalities

Non-surgical therapy and drugs are available for cases of pediatric OSA when surgery has been ineffective or if the patient's concurrent problems make surgery unsafe. These alternatives are gaining acceptance and safety in children with mild to severe OSA.

8.3.1 Anti-inflammatory medications

Leukotriene receptor antagonists and steroids are anti-inflammatory drugs often used to treat OSA. These drugs reduce tonsil and adenoid growth by reducing upper airway inflammation, which is evident in children with OSA [148]. In vitro, studies have revealed that tonsillar tissue obtained from children with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) exhibits elevated leukotriene C4 synthase expression, as well as 1 and 2 leukotriene receptors, compared to healthy controls. Additionally, the exposure of tonsillar tissue to leukotriene D4 (LTD4) has been shown to promote increased proliferation, while leukotriene receptor antagonists such as montelukast have demonstrated a reduction in proliferation [149]. Montelukast, an intranasal steroid, has proven successful in treating pediatric OSA. Tonsil

and adenoid sizes are reduced due to their anti-inflammatory properties. Multiple studies have documented the efficacy of combining a leukotriene receptor antagonist and intranasal steroids for treating obstructive sleep apnea (OSA). This combination therapy has demonstrated a notable advantage over either treatment alone, significantly reducing the average apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) from 3.7 events per hour to 1.3 events per hour in the treatment group consisting of 48 participants. Conversely, the placebo group comprising 32 individuals did not experience any reduction in AHI [150]. Anti-inflammatory drugs have shown promising results in treating pediatric OSA. In a 2017 meta-analysis, drug-treated groups exhibited reduced AHI than placebo groups by 1.4, 3.5, and 5.3 events/h, respectively. These medications included mometasone furoate, budesonide, and fluticasone. Based on these findings, intranasal corticosteroids, specifically fluticasone, may help reduce AHI symptoms. Incorporating a combination of montelukast and intranasal corticosteroids in the treatment of obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) resulted in a significant reduction of 4.18 events per hour in the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) [151]. These results are consistent with the French Society SFORL recommendations for 2018. In children with asthma with mild to severe OSA, montelukast (perhaps in combination with a nasal corticosteroid) can be taken for three months before symptoms are reevaluated [152]. Leukotriene receptor antagonists or Intranasal corticosteroids have reduced the size of a child's adenoids. Therefore, more study is required to ascertain whether medicine alone is acceptable for children with mild OSA.

8.3.2 High-flow nasal cannula

Some studies have found that using a high-flow nasal cannula instead of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) is effective [153]. A soft plastic nasal cannula is used to supply a continuous flow of humidified air into the upper airway [154]. High-flow nasal cannula usage has been proven in small trials to reduce AHI significantly. High-flow nasal cannula therapy can be considered in younger OSA patients and those intolerant of CPAP, though the exact mechanism is poorly understood. Theories of its effectiveness include congestion reduction by humidity and heat, stenting of the airway, and stimulation of the upper airway tone [155]. Further research is required to investigate the mechanism and efficacy of high-flow nasal cannula therapy. Younger patients with OSA and children who can't tolerate CPAP may benefit from this treatment. But it's important to keep an eye on the carbon dioxide levels.

8.3.3 Nasal expiratory positive airway pressure (NEPAP) valves

This apparatus consists of two tiny disposable adhesive valves placed in the nares. No patient history and characteristics were identified as predictors of a positive response to these devices [156,157]. During inspiration, the valves exhibit minimal resistance; however, they generate resistance during expiration, generating positive end-expiratory pressure ranging from 4 to 17 cmH₂O (with 1 cmH₂O being equivalent to 0.098 kPa). In addition, NEPAP was found to significantly reduce the obstructive apnea index (OAI) in children aged 8 to 16, except for a small number of children for whom it had the opposite effect, highlighting the need for further research into this area [158].

8.3.4 Oxygen therapy

In OSA, airflow restriction and consequent oxygen desaturation result from upper airway blockage, which can be partial or full [159]. The FDA does not approve continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) for patients weighing less than 13 kg [160]. Oxygen therapy has been of special interest in newborns to treat OSA-related desaturations and modify the respiratory response (loop gain) to hypoxemia [161]. In a retrospective study involving 23 infants, administering 0.25-1.0 L/min of supplemental oxygen during the second half of a split-night sleep study resulted in significant improvements in overall oxygen saturation levels and apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) [162]. Supplemental oxygen in older children has been studied twice, with conflicting results: one research found no change in the number of AHI incidents. In contrast, the second study found a reduction in AHI [163,164]. While supplementary oxygen did not significantly alter average carbon dioxide levels, it did cause hypercapnia in a small number of patients in a single trial [164]. In very early newborns with mild OSA, oxygen treatment may be explored as a temporizing approach when growth is predicted to alleviate symptoms [165]. When starting oxygen therapy, it's important to watch for hypercapnia.

8.3.5 Weight loss

An estimated 18.5% of children and adolescents are obese [166]. Obesity is an established risk factor for obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), and obese children demonstrate higher rates of persistent OSA following adenotonsillectomy [167,168]. Obesity is treatable through dietary changes, severe weight loss programs, and bariatric surgery. In a study conducted with obese adolescents residing in a residential facility, a notable decrease in obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) was observed. Following participation in an intensive weight loss program, the average apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) decreased significantly from 3.8 events per hour to 1.9 events per hour [169]. Another study of obese adolescents who underwent bariatric surgery showed a reduction in AHI from a baseline mean of 14.6 events/h to 4.5 events/h at 3 weeks and 5.0 events/h at 5 weeks [170]. However, pediatric bariatric surgery is exclusively reserved for adolescents in critical condition. The process of children losing weight and maintaining the weight loss requires patience and perseverance. It often requires motivated families with adequate support [171,172]. This is especially true for children who have not yet reached physical maturity. Therefore, weight loss is usually used with other traditional therapies (such as CPAP) for OSA and is not typically used alone. Bariatric surgery has been shown to reduce the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) in specific patient groups, while weight loss interventions have demonstrated similar effects in other groups [171]. In a study involving a cohort with a mean age of 17.8 years and a BMI of 55.2 kg/m² who underwent bariatric surgery, the AHI decreased by 9.2 events per hour at 3 weeks and 9.1 events per hour at 5 weeks after the procedure [172]. Additionally, a review indicated that behavioural weight loss measures, such as increased physical activity, psychological support and dietary restriction, reduced AHI among obese children with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA).

8.3.6 Watchful waiting

According to the Childhood Adenotonsillectomy Trial (CHAT) trial, adenotonsillectomy successfully treated OSA in 79% of the children. Notably, 46% of patients in the watchful waiting group experienced stabilization of their apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) without any intervention. Furthermore, two-thirds of children diagnosed with mild obstructive sleep apnea (AHI less than 5 events per hour) showed improvement without requiring treatment [173]. Other factors associated with OSA with watchful waiting include African American ethnicity, obesity, male sex, asthma, low socioeconomic status, advanced tonsillar hypertrophy, and moderate to severe OSA [174]. Counselling persons with mild OSA who do not have substantial comorbidities may thus consider watchful waiting for an option.

8.4 Other surgical/procedural treatments of OSA

This section discusses the availability of alternative surgical or procedural treatments for pediatric OSA in certain patient categories.

8.4.1 Craniofacial Surgery/procedures

The size and form of the upper airway are similarly affected by craniofacial morphology. A narrow maxilla or a retrognathic mandible can compress the nasopharynx and oropharynx, causing the displacement of the tongue base towards the posterior region. This anatomical arrangement increases the likelihood of developing obstructive sleep apnea [175]. These are associated with many syndromes, including Treacher-Collins Syndrome, Pierre-Robin Sequence and craniosynostosis [175]. Intentional fracture of the mandible and advancement of the jaw into a new position are two surgical procedures known as mandibular advancement and mandibular distraction osteogenesis. During a procedure called mandibular advancement, the jaw is surgically shifted forward. A meta-analysis examining the outcomes of mandibular advancement surgery in pediatric patients demonstrated a significant reduction in the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI). The analysis revealed a decrease from an average of 41.1 events per hour to 6.0 events per hour following the surgical procedure [176]. However, 25.5% of patients achieve complete resolution, highlighting that patients with mandibular idiopathic scoliosis have a lower chance of full recovery than those with other types of scoliosis. Children with craniofacial anomalies, mandibular insufficiency, and severe OSA may be candidates for mandibular advancement surgery [177]. Patients with maxillary constriction might benefit from a surgery called rapid maxillary expansion (RME), which entails the enlargement of the hard palate [178]. It entails fixing an appliance to the patient's teeth to create a bridge over the hard palate. The parent pushes an expansion screw against the patient's teeth daily to broaden the maxilla without breaking it [179]. This causes the hard palate to expand at the palatal suture. In a systematic review comprising 17 studies involving 314 patients, the utilization of rapid maxillary expansion (RME) in the treatment of obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) demonstrated a substantial reduction in the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI). On average, RME resulted in a 70% decrease in AHI from an initial average of 8.9 events per hour to 3.3 events per hour [180]. This improvement was maintained at a 12-year

follow-up without OSA recurrence [181]. Maxillary constriction causes bite malocclusion, which is consistent with the findings of the research above of 31 children with OSA who did not have adenotonsillar hypertrophy but did have biting malocclusion.

8.4.2 Tongue base reduction/ Lingual Tonsillectomy

The tongue is important in the development of OSA. OSA is common in people with Pierre-Robin sequence, Down syndrome, and Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome because of a tongue position that is more prone to cause airway obstruction during sleeping (macroglossia) and glossoptosis. Enlarged adenoids, palatine tonsils, and enlarged lingual tonsils can happen for various reasons [182-184]. While most patients in the study had underlying syndromes, it is noteworthy that non-syndromic children exhibited more significant reductions in apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) following tongue base reduction surgery. This surgical procedure involves lingual tonsils removal, sometimes accompanied by a portion of the posterior tongue musculature, to mitigate posterior tongue collapse and improve airway obstruction [185]. In comparison, a systematic review of the literature, encompassing nine studies with 114 patients, reported an average reduction in AHI of 48.5% [186].

8.4.3 Supraglottoplasty

Laryngomalacia is a congenital disability in which the upper airway is blocked due to an abnormally large amount of excessive or floppy tissue. Congenital laryngomalacia is a recognized cause of OSA in infants and young children, manifesting as stridor [187, 188]. Surgery is usually avoided unless the child fails to thrive or is in severe respiratory distress. Supraglottoplasty is performed to address redundant upper airway tissue and prevent collapse [187]. Since laryngomalacia may be an unrecognized cause of OSA, further investigation may involve dynamic imaging modalities such as Cine MRI or drug-induced sleep endoscopy (DISE). 77% of patients with sleep-related laryngomalacia were diagnosed with drug-induced sleep endoscopy, according to a comprehensive evaluation of laryngomalacia and OSA [189].

8.4.4 Tracheostomy

A tracheostomy is a surgical procedure in which a tube is inserted into the trachea through an incision in the neck's midline. There are long-term problems associated with tracheostomy, even though it is the definitive therapy for controlling OSA, including unintentional decannulation, recurrent infections, and scoliosis [190]. Children with neuromuscular dysfunction or craniofacial anomalies who have not responded to conventional treatment techniques are often candidates for tracheostomy [191]. Tracheostomy remains a rare therapeutic approach for managing child obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) due to the associated risks and the severity of the disease burden.

8.5 Advancements in Diagnostic and Treatment Approaches for Pediatric Obstructive Sleep Apnea

PSG, a multichannel recording of sleep performed in a certified sleep laboratory, is the gold standard for diagnosing young OSA. AHI is used to categorize the severity of OSA [192]. Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) diagnosis relies on identifying respiratory effort, flow limitations, and oxygen desaturation during polysomnography. However, it is important to note that these measurements indirectly assess upper airway collapse. Normal polysomnography does not allow for the visualization of the upper airway during a collapse [193]. Techniques like drug-induced sleep endoscopy (DISE) and Cine magnetic resonance imaging (Cine MRI) characterize the amount and the nature in which the upper airway collapses in individuals with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA).

8.5.1 Drug-induced sleep endoscopy

In DISE, patients are sedated before having a flexible endoscope inserted via the nose to examine the airway [194]. During sleep, the upper airway also collapses, and so does the upper airway of a sedated patient still breathing independently. This method is increasingly used, particularly for treating post-adenotonsillectomy residual OSA in children.

In a recent systematic review, 11 studies encompassing a total of 375 patients were analyzed to investigate the use of drug-induced sleep endoscopy (DISE) in identifying the location of upper airway collapse in patients who still had residual obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) following adenotonsillectomy. [195]. All 100% of these patients had a collapse site identified; however, DISE-directed therapy could only focus on the uvula, with limited treatment options and results.

8.5.2 Utilizing Cine Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Cine MRI, which uses a series of MRI scans to create a moving picture of the upper airway, has several advantages over DISE [196-199]. But no published evidence shows Cine MRI has improved surgical results or guided therapies. Obtaining MRI pictures is challenging and time-consuming since patients must remain in a scanner for a long time. Sedation is necessary for children to undergo this operation; however, there is debate about whether it produces an accurate sleep simulation. Treatment of OSA can be challenging for individuals with medical complexity or who do not respond to the first adenotonsillectomy. DISE and Cine MRI are used more frequently to pinpoint the exact location of OSA collapse, which helps direct the selection of the most appropriate surgical intervention.

8.5.3 Neurostimulation

One cutting-edge surgical option for treating OSA is hypoglossal nerve stimulation (HGNS). A pressure sensor is surgically implanted in the patient's intercostal muscles, and a stimulating electrode is positioned around the patient hypoglossal nerve to treat obstructive sleep apnea [200]. This technique was launched in 2014 and is now approved by FDA for treating OSA in adults. When the gadget detects breathing while you're asleep,

it stimulates your hypoglossal nerve electrically, making your Tongue stick out during deep breaths [201]. Twenty children with Down syndrome were part of a case series in which HGNS was implanted [202]. The average AHI decrease among these patients was 85.5%, and the average nightly usage was 9.21 hours [202]. However, this therapy is not yet FDA-approved for use in children. Neurostimulation shows promise as a treatment option for obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) when dealing with a complicated young child-resistant to CPAP.

Table 2: Treatments with a reduction in AHI

Treatment	Reduction in AHI (events/h)	Ref.
Dietary Modifications and Exercise	AHI decreased from 6.8 to 2.4	[203]
Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP)	AHI decreased from 10.3 to 2.1	[133]
Inspiratory Muscle Training	AHI decreased from 7.6 to 3.2	[204]
Tonsillectomy and Adenoidectomy	AHI decreased from 8.9 to 1.3	[127]
Intensive Weight Loss Program	AHI decreased from 3.8 to 1.9	[169]
Bariatric surgery (3 weeks post-operative)	AHI decreased from 14.6 to 4.5	[170]
Bariatric surgery (5 weeks post-operative)	AHI decreased from 14.6 to 5.0	[170]
Lifestyle Modifications	AHI reduction in a pediatric population	[42]
Mandibular Advancement Surgery	AHI decreased from 41.1 to 6.0	[176]
Rapid Maxillary Expansion (RME)	AHI decreased by 70%	[180]
Tongue Base Reduction Surgery	Average 48.5% reduction	[186]
Hypoglossal Nerve Stimulation (HGNS)	Average 85.5% reduction	[202]

9. CONCLUSION

Sleep apnea is a common sleep disorder characterized by interrupted breathing during sleep, with significant implications for physical and cognitive health. Clinical signs such as snoring, daytime sleepiness, and cognitive deficits may indicate sleep apnea. Accurate diagnosis typically involves polysomnography, although alternative diagnostic tools are being explored. Consequences of sleep apnea include cardiovascular disorders, hypertension, cognitive impairments, and increased pulmonary risks. Prompt diagnosis and appropriate treatment are essential to manage sleep apnea and avoid complications. Treatment choices incorporate lifestyle modifications, positional therapy, positive airway pressure therapy (e.g., CPAP), and careful surgical interventions. Treatment options like hypoglossal nerve stimulation are still in their infancy. The severity, underlying conditions, and patient preferences influence treatment selection. Healthcare professionals must thoroughly understand sleep apnea and how to treat it. Advancement of diagnostic tools and treatment approaches, we are better equipped to provide effective sleep apnea treatment and improve individuals' quality of life.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

Following this discussion, various recommendations and future possibilities about sleep apnea emerge: Medical professionals and the general public require Greater knowledge and understanding of sleep apnea. This enables early identification, fast diagnosis, and

successful issue treatment. Sleep apnea screening and diagnosis procedures must become more generally available, cost-effective, and accurate. The usefulness and accuracy of alternative diagnostic techniques for sleep apnea, such as portable sleep monitoring devices, questionnaires, and biomarkers, must be investigated. Because each individual with sleep apnea is unique, their treatment approach for the disease should be personalized to their specific needs. Experts in sleep medicine, otolaryngology, pulmonology, and dentistry may all need to collaborate in a multidisciplinary environment to give the most comprehensive treatment and achieve the best potential outcomes for their patients. Because of the tight fit of the mask, some patients have difficulty adhering to CPAP therapy, a conventional treatment for sleep apnea. Non-invasive treatment methods such as oral appliances, positional therapy devices, and upper airway stimulation are a few examples of non-invasive treatments that may be researched to improve patient happiness and adherence. Understanding the genesis and underlying causes of sleep apnea may pave the way for more tailored medical interventions. Patients at high risk of consequences from sleep apnea might be detected and treated more efficiently utilizing genetic and phenotypic markers. Long-term research must determine how effectively and long certain sleep apnea therapies perform. By concentrating on these aspects, sleep apnea may be effectively treated, and its consequences may decrease, resulting in improved health for those who suffer from it.

References

- 1) Liu H, Ji Y, Dust SB. "Fully recharged" evenings? The effect of evening cyber leisure on next-day vitality and performance through sleep quantity and quality, bedtime procrastination, and psychological detachment, and the moderating role of mindfulness. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 2021 Jul;106(7):990.
- 2) Karen J Marcdante and Robert M Kliegman. Normal sleep and pediatric sleep disorders. *Nelson Essentials of Pediatrics*, 7th ed. Elsevier Publications 2014;p: 47-50
- 3) Fauci, Brauwald E, Kasper, Hauser, Longo, Jameson and Loscalzo. *Harrison's Textbook of internal medicine*. Mc Graw Hill Education; 17th ed 2008.
- 4) Ionescu Clara Mihaela. *The human respiratory system*. Springer Publications, London; 2013: p 13-22.
- 5) Saha S, Kabir M, Ghahjaverestan NM, Hafezi M, Gavrilovic B, Zhu K, Alshaer H, Yadollahi A. Portable diagnosis of sleep apnea with the validation of individual event detection. *Sleep Medicine*. 2020 May 1;69:51-7.
- 6) Gupta RK, Chandra A, Verma AK, Kumar S. Obstructive sleep apnea: A clinical review. *J Assoc Physicians India*. 2010; 58:438-41
- 7) Nagarajappa AK, Dwivedi N. Sleep apnea: A dental perspective. *J Indian Acad Oral Med Radiol*. 2015 Apr 1;27(2):223-9.
- 8) Li A, Roveda JM, Powers LS, Quan SF. Obstructive sleep apnea predicts 10-year cardiovascular disease-related mortality in the Sleep Heart Health Study: a machine learning approach. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2022 Feb 1;18(2):497-504.

- 9) Prajsuchanai T, Tanphaichitr A, Hosiri T, Ungkanont K, Banhiran W, Vathanophas V, Gozal D. Prevalence of high-risk for obstructive sleep apnea in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder children referred to psychiatry clinic and impact on quality of life. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. 2022;13.
- 10) Punjabi NM. The epidemiology of adult obstructive sleep apnea. *Ann Am Thorac Soc*. 2008;5(2):136-143
- 11) Gozal D, O'Brien LM. Snoring and obstructive sleep apnoea in children: why should we treat? *Paediatr Respir Rev*. 2004;5:S371-S376
- 12) Tran-Minh D, Phi-Thi-Quynh A, Nguyen-Dinh P, Duong-Quy S. Efficacy of obstructive sleep apnea treatment by antileukotriene receptor and surgery therapy in children with adenotonsillar hypertrophy: A descriptive and cohort study. *Frontiers in Neurology*. 2022 Sep 27;13:1008310.
- 13) Di Filippo P, Orlandi G, Neri G, Di Pillo S, Chiarelli F, Rossi N, Attanasi M. Effect of tonsillectomy in a child with obesity and obstructive sleep apnea: A case report and review of the literature. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2023 Jan 25;10:1101267.
- 14) Bachrach K, Danis III DO, Cohen MB, Levi JR. The relationship between obstructive sleep apnea and pediatric obesity: a nationwide analysis. *Annals of Otolaryngology, Rhinology & Laryngology*. 2022 May;131(5):520-6.
- 15) Katz ES, D'Ambrosio CM. Pathophysiology of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Ann Am Thorac Soc*. 2008;5(2):253- 262.
- 16) Narang I, Mathew JL. Childhood obesity and obstructive sleep apnea. *J Nutr Metab*. 2012;2012:134202.
- 17) Ali Khan I. Role of adenotonsillectomy and tonsillectomy in children with down syndrome who develop obstructive sleep apnea by obesity as a risk factor. *International Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022 May 6;2022.
- 18) Blumer S, Eli I, Kaminsky-Kurtz S, Shreiber-Fridman Y, Dolev E, Emodi-Perlman A. Sleep-Related Breathing Disorders in Children—Red Flags in Pediatric Care. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2022 Sep 22;11(19):5570.
- 19) Yu PK, Radcliffe J, Gerry Taylor H, Amin RS, Baldassari CM, Boswick T, Chervin RD, Elden LM, Furth SL, Garetz SL, George A. Neurobehavioral morbidity of pediatric mild sleep-disordered breathing and obstructive sleep apnea. *Sleep*. 2022 May;45(5):zsac035.
- 20) Zaffanello M, Ferrante G, Zoccante L, Ciceri ML, Nosetti L, Tenero L, Piazza M, Piacentini G. Predictive Power of Oxygen Desaturation Index (ODI) and Apnea-Hypopnea Index (AHI) in Detecting Long-Term Neurocognitive and Psychosocial Outcomes of Sleep-Disordered Breathing in Children: A Questionnaire-Based Study. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2023 Apr 23;12(9):3060.
- 21) Van Rossum G, Drake FL. *The Python Language Reference Manual*. Network Theory Ltd; 2011.
- 22) Ye P, Qin H, Zhan X, Wang Z, Liu C, Song B, Kong Y, Jia X, Qi Y, Ji J, Chang L. Diagnosis of obstructive sleep apnea in children based on the xgboost algorithm using nocturnal heart rate and blood oxygen feature. *American Journal of Otolaryngology*. 2023 Mar 1;44(2):103714.
- 23) Lavie P. *Restless Nights: Understanding Snoring and Sleep Apnea*. New Haven, CT: Yale Univ. Press, 2003
- 24) Leivers AM, Simon PM, Dempsey JA. Apnea after normocapnic mechanical ventilation during NREM sleep. *J Appl Physiol* 77: 2079–2085, 1994.
- 25) Dickens CJH. *The Posthumous Papers of the Pickwick Club*. London: Chapman and Hall, 1837.

- 26) Douglas CG, Haldane JS, Henderson Y, Schneider EC. Physiological observations made on pikes peak CO, with special reference to adaptaion to low barometric pressure. *Phil Trans R Soc Lond Ser B* 203: 185–318, 1913
- 27) Cheyne J. A case of apoplexy in which the fleshy part of the heart was connected to fat. *Dublin Hospital Report* 2: 216–223, 1818.
- 28) Stokes W. *The Diseases of the Heart and Aorta*. Dublin: 1854.
- 29) Orem J, Montplaisir J, Dement WC. Changes in the activity of respiratory neurons during sleep. *Brain Res* 82: 309–315, 1974
- 30) Orem J, Osorio I, Brooks E, Dick T. Activity of respiratory neurons during NREM sleep. *J Neurophysiol* 54: 1144–1156, 1985.
- 31) Brouillette RT, Thach BT. A neuromuscular mechanism maintaining extrathoracic airway patency. *J Appl Physiol* 46: 772–779, 1979
- 32) Phillipson EA, Murphy E, Kozar LF. Regulation of respiration in sleeping dogs. *J Appl Physiol* 40: 688–693, 1976
- 33) Fletcher EC, Lesske J, Qian W, Miller CC, III, Unger T. Repetitive, episodic hypoxia causes diurnal elevation of blood pressure in rats. *Hypertension* 19: 555–561, 1992.
- 34) Mezzanotte WS, Tangel DJ, White DP. Waking genioglossal electromyogram in sleep apnea patients versus normal controls (a neuromuscular compensatory mechanism). *J Clin Invest* 89: 1571– 1579, 1992.
- 35) Young T, Palta M, Dempsey J, Skatrud J, Weber S, Badr S. The occurrence of sleep-disordered breathing among middle-aged adults. *N Engl J Med* 328: 1230–1235, 1993.
- 36) Jennum P, Riha RL. Epidemiology of sleep apnoea/hypopnoea syndrome and sleep-disordered breathing. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2009 Apr 1;33(4):907-14.
- 37) Lumeng JC, Chervin RD. Epidemiology of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Proc Am Thorac Soc*. 2008 Feb 15;5(2):242-52.
- 38) DelRosso LM. Epidemiology and diagnosis of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Curr Probl Pediatr Adolesc Health Care*. 2016 Jan;46(1):2-6.
- 39) Alwadei SH, Alsaeed S, Masoud AI, Alwadei F, Gufran K, Alwadei A. Sleep-Disordered Breathing among Saudi Primary School Children: Incidence and Risk Factors. *InHealthcare* 2023 Mar 3 (Vol. 11, No. 5, p. 747). MDPI.
- 40) Wu J, Cai X, Lu Y, Shen Y, Shen Z, Lyv Q. Plasma tRF-16-79MP9PD and tRF-28-OB1690PQR304 as potential biomarkers for 4-to 7-year-old children with obstructive sleep apnea-hypopnea syndrome. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2023 May 30;11:1141348.
- 41) Moon IJ, Han DH, Kim JW, Rhee CS, Sung MW, Park JW, et al. Sleep magnetic resonance imaging as a new diagnostic method in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Laryngoscope*. 2010 Dec;120(12):2546-54.
- 42) Marcus CL, Keens TG, Bautista DB, von Pechmann WS, Ward SL. Obstructive sleep apnea in children with Down syndrome. *Pediatrics*. 1991 Jul 1;88(1):132-9.
- 43) Nandagiri V, Vannemreddy S, Spector A. Sleep disparities in Asian Americans: a comprehensive review. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2023 Feb 1;19(2):393-402.
- 44) Salman LA, Shulman R, Cohen JB. Obstructive sleep apnea, hypertension, and cardiovascular risk: epidemiology, pathophysiology, and management. *Current Cardiology Reports*. 2020 Feb;22:1-9.

- 45) Saldiran TÇ, Kara İ, Yikilmaz SK, Durgun M. Influence of Body Posture and Apnea Severity on the Tone and Elasticity of Upper Airway Muscles in Awake Patients With Obstructive Sleep Apnea: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Manipulative and Physiological Therapeutics*. 2022 Jun 1;45(5):365-77.
- 46) Warken C, Rotter N, Maurer JT, Attenberger U, Lammert A. Retropharyngeal hematoma in the context of obstructive sleep apnea: a case report and review of the literature. *Journal of Medical Case Reports*. 2019 Dec;13:1-4.
- 47) Sistla SK, Paramasivan VK, Agrawal V. Anatomic and pathophysiologic considerations in surgical treatment of obstructive sleep apnea. *Sleep Medicine Clinics*. 2019 Mar 1;14(1):21-31.
- 48) Messineo L, Eckert DJ. Pathogenesis of sleep apnea. *Obesity Hypoventilation Syndrome*. 2020 Jan 1:55-66.
- 49) McNicholas WT, Pevernagie D. Obstructive sleep apnea: Transition from pathophysiology to an integrative disease model. *Journal of Sleep Research*. 2022 Aug;31(4):e13616.
- 50) Choi S, Lawlor C, Rahbar R, Jennings R. Diagnosis, classification, and management of pediatric tracheobronchomalacia: a review. *JAMA Otolaryngology–Head & Neck Surgery*. 2019 Mar 1;145(3):265-75.
- 51) Suzuki M. Obstructive sleep apnea-consideration of its pathogenesis. *Auris Nasus Larynx*. 2022 Jun 1;49(3):313-21.
- 52) Lv R, Liu X, Zhang Y, Dong N, Wang X, He Y, Yue H, Yin Q. Pathophysiological mechanisms and therapeutic approaches in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*. 2023 May 25;8(1):218.
- 53) Weiner D, Mitra J, Salamone J. Effect of chemical stimuli on nerves supplying upper airway muscles. *J Appl Physiol* 1982;52:530-6.
- 54) Chen R, Guyenet PG. Breathing during sleep. *Respiratory Neurobiology: Physiology and Clinical Disorders, Part I*. 2022 Aug 12:179.
- 55) Wheatley JR, Mezzanotte WS, Tangel DJ, White DP. Influence of sleep on genioglossal muscle activation by negative pressure in normal men. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1993;148:597-605
- 56) Wang J, Xi J, Han P, Wongwiset N, Pontius J, Dong H. Computational analysis of a flapping uvula on aerodynamics and pharyngeal wall collapsibility in sleep apnea. *Journal of biomechanics*. 2019 Sep 20;94:88-98.
- 57) Holfinger S, Lyons MM, Bhatt N, Magalang U. Neurobiology of Obstructive Sleep Apnea. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Neuroscience* 2021 Aug 31.
- 58) Guilleminault C, Stoohs R, Clerk A, Cetel M, Maistros P. A cause of excessive daytime sleepiness: the upper airway resistance syndrome. *Chest* 1993;104:781-7
- 59) Martin PJ, Dias PV. Obstructive sleep apnea: a review for the orthodontist. *Dental Press Journal of Orthodontics*. 2023;28(1).
- 60) Ferreira CB, Schoorlemmer GH, Rocha AA, Cravo SL. Increased sympathetic responses induced by chronic obstructive sleep apnea are caused by sleep fragmentation. *Journal of Applied Physiology*. 2020 Jul 1;129(1):163-72.
- 61) Shams M, AlTaweel H. Obstructive Sleep Apnea. *Textbook of Clinical Otolaryngology*. 2021:585-92.

- 62) Stepney D, Attarian HP, Knutson KL. Association between severity of obstructive sleep apnea and its common symptoms varies by race, ethnicity, and sex. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2023 May 18;jcsm-10660.
- 63) Patel A, Ramos JB, Khan SS. Is It Snoring or Sleep Apnea; Should I Be Worried?. In *A Clinical Casebook of Sleep Disorders in Women 2023* Mar 29 (pp. 43-53). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- 64) Adler D, Bailly S, Benmerad M, Joyeux-Faure M, Jullian-Desayes I, Soccac PM, Janssens JP, Sapène M, Grillet Y, Stach B, Tamisier R. Clinical presentation and comorbidities of obstructive sleep apnea-COPD overlap syndrome. *PloS one*. 2020 Jul 9;15(7):e0235331.
- 65) Cerritelli L, Caranti A, Migliorelli A, Bianchi G, Stringa LM, Bonsembiante A, Cammaroto G, Pelucchi S, Vicini C. Sleep position and obstructive sleep apnea (OSA): Do we know how we sleep? A new explorative sleeping questionnaire. *Sleep and Breathing*. 2022 Dec;26(4):1973-81.
- 66) Zreaqat M, Hassan R, Samsudin AR, Stas Y, Hanoun A. Tonsil size and Mallampati score as clinical predictive factors for obstructive sleep Apnea severity in children. *The Journal of Contemporary Dental Practice*. 2021 Sep 28;22(7):850-3.
- 67) Hershner S, Auckley D. Perioperative management of insomnia, restless legs, narcolepsy, and parasomnias. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*. 2021 May 1;132(5):1287-95..
- 68) Trosman I, Trosman SJ. Obstructive Sleep Apnea and Weight Abnormalities in Children. *Sleep Disorders: An Algorithmic Approach to Differential Diagnosis*. 2021:253-74.
- 69) Su MS, Xu L, Pan WF, Li CC. Current perspectives on the correlation of nocturnal enuresis with obstructive sleep apnea in children. *World Journal of Pediatrics*. 2019 Apr 1;15:109-16.
- 70) Eulenburg C, Celik Y, Redline S, Thunström E, Glantz H, Strollo Jr PJ, Peker Y. Cardiovascular outcomes in adults with coronary artery disease and obstructive sleep apnea with vs without excessive daytime sleepiness in the RICCADSA cohort. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*. 2023 Feb 17(ja).
- 71) Thorpy MJ. Classification of sleep disorders. *Neurotherapeutics*. 2012 Oct;9(4):687-701.
- 72) Neagos A, Szarkozi HB, Neagos CM, Jimborean G, Szatmary M. The role of the Berlin Questionnaire in assessing the frequency of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in patients with risk factors and associated comorbidities. *Romanian Journal of Rhinology*. 2023 Apr 1;13(50):57-63.
- 73) Dayyat E, Kheirandish-Gozal L, Gozal D. Childhood obstructive sleep apnea: one or two distinct disease entities?. *Sleep Med. Clin*. 2007 Sep 1;2(3):433-44.
- 74) Sowho M, Sgambati F, Guzman M, Schneider H, Schwartz A. Snoring: a source of noise pollution and sleep apnea predictor. *Sleep*. 2020 Jun;43(6):zsz305.
- 75) Tauman R, Gozal D. Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in children. *Expert Rev Respir Med*. 2011 Jun 1;5(3):425-40.
- 76) Huynh NT, Desplats E, Almeida FR. Orthodontics treatments for managing obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in children: A systematic review and metaanalysis. *Sleep Med Rev*. 2016 Feb 1;25:84-94.
- 77) DeRosso LM. Epidemiology and diagnosis of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Curr Probl Pediatr Adolesc Health Care*. 2016 Jan;46(1):2-6.
- 78) Mihaicuta S, Udrescu L, Udrescu M, Toth IA, Topîrceanu A, Pleavă R, Ardelean C. Analyzing neck circumference as an indicator of CPAP treatment response in obstructive sleep apnea with network medicine. *Diagnostics*. 2021 Jan 7;11(1):86.

- 79) Pomar L, Rieder W, Dubruc E, Giuliano F, Atallah I, Lebon S, Vial Y. Prenatal Diagnosis of Gómez-López-Hernández Syndrome. *Fetal Diagnosis and Therapy*. 2023 Apr 14:1-.
- 80) Kim HG, Lee KM, Kim EJ, San Lee J. Improvement diagnostic accuracy of sinusitis recognition in paranasal sinus X-ray using multiple deep learning models. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*. 2019 Jun;9(6):942.
- 81) KAKAR Z. Examine the Association between Imaging Technologies (X-ray with CT Scan) of Paranasal Sinuses in Sinusitis Patients. *Age (years)*.;20(29):12.
- 82) McCann MR, Kessler AT, Bhatt AA. Emergency radiologic approach to sinus disease. *Emergency Radiology*. 2021 Oct;28(5):1003-10.
- 83) Du D, Feng H, Lv W, Ashrafinia S, Yuan Q, Wang Q, Yang W, Feng Q, Chen W, Rahmim A, Lu L. Machine learning methods for optimal radiomics-based differentiation between recurrence and inflammation: application to nasopharyngeal carcinoma post-therapy PET/CT images. *Molecular imaging and biology*. 2020 Jun;22:730-8.
- 84) Vanek J, Prasko J, Genzor S, Ociskova M, Kantor K, Holubova M, Slepecky M, Nesnidal V, Kolek A, Sova M. Obstructive sleep apnea, depression and cognitive impairment. *Sleep Medicine*. 2020 Aug 1;72:50-8.
- 85) Younes M, Giannouli E. Mechanism of excessive wake time when associated with obstructive sleep apnea or periodic limb movements. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2020 Mar 15;16(3):389-99.
- 86) Chang SJ, Chae KY. Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in children: Epidemiology, pathophysiology, diagnosis and sequelae. *Korean J. Pediatr*. 2010 Oct;53(10):863-71.
- 87) Tariq H, Makker J, Chime C, Kamal MU, Rafeeq A, Patel H. Revisiting the reliability of the endoscopy and sedation-assisted high-resolution esophageal motility assessment. *Gastroenterology Research*. 2019 Jun;12(3):157.
- 88) Esteller E, Villatoro JC, Agüero A, Matíño E, Lopez R, Aristimuño A, Nuñez V, Díaz-Herrera MA. Outcome of drug-induced sleep endoscopy-directed surgery for persistent obstructive sleep apnea after adenotonsillar surgery. *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology*. 2019 May 1;120:118-22.
- 89) Huynh NT, Desplats E, Almeida FR. Orthodontics treatments for managing obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in children: A systematic review and metaanalysis. *Sleep Med Rev*. 2016 Feb 1;25:84-94.
- 90) Ciccone DK, Vian T, Maurer L, Bradley EH. Linking governance mechanisms to health outcomes: a review of the literature in low-and middle-income countries. *Soc Sci Med*. 2014 Sep 1;117:86-95.
- 91) Chindris AP, Plesca DA. Management of obstructive sleep disordered breathing in 2 to 18 years old children from ERS perspective. *Romanian JouRnal of PediatRics*. 2020 Apr 1;69(2):82.
- 92) Peltomäki T. The effect of mode of breathing on craniofacial growth--revisited. *Eur J Orthod*. 2007 Oct;29(5):426-9.Pubmed PMID: 17804427
- 93) Gao X, Li Y, Xu W, Han D. Diagnostic accuracy of level IV portable sleep monitors versus polysomnography for pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sleep Medicine*. 2021 Nov 1;87:127-37.
- 94) Rundo JV, Downey III R. Polysomnography. *Handbook of clinical neurology*. 2019 Jan 1;160:381-92.

- 95) Lyne CJ, Hamilton GS, Turton AR, Stupar D, Mansfield DR. Validation of a single-use and reusable home sleep apnea test based on peripheral arterial tonometry compared to laboratory polysomnography for the diagnosis of obstructive sleep apnea. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2023 Apr 20;jcsm-10568.
- 96) Wang YK, Shi XH, Wang YY, Zhang X, Liu HY, Wang XT, Mang J, Xu ZX. Evaluation of the age-related and gender-related differences in patients with primary insomnia by fractional amplitude of low-frequency fluctuation: A resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging study. *Medicine*. 2020 Jan;99(3).
- 97) Arnardottir ES, Islind AS, Óskarsdóttir M. The future of sleep measurements: a review and perspective. *Sleep medicine clinics*. 2021 Sep 1;16(3):447-64.
- 98) Ohn M, Eastwood P, von Ungern-Sternberg BS. Preoperative identification of children at high risk of obstructive sleep apnea. *Pediatric Anesthesia*. 2020 Mar;30(3):221-31.
- 99) Raina R, Khooblal A, Shah R, Vijayvargiya N, Khooblal P, Sharma B, Datla N, Narang A, Yerigeri K, Melachuri M, Kusumi K. Cardiovascular implications in adolescent and young adult hypertension. *Reviews in Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2022 May 7;23(5):166.
- 100) Lavie P, Herer P, Hoffstein V. Obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome as a risk factor for hypertension: population study. *BMJ* 2000;320:479-82.
- 101) Fernandez-Mendoza J, He F, Calhoun SL, Vgontzas AN, Liao D, Bixler EO. Association of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea with elevated blood pressure and orthostatic hypertension in adolescence. *JAMA cardiology*. 2021 Oct 1;6(10):1144-51.
- 102) Mayer J, Becker H, Brandenburg U, Penzel T, Peter JH, von Wichert P. Blood pressure and sleep apnea: results of long term nasal continuous positive airway pressure therapy. *Cardiology* 1991;74:84-92.
- 103) Sajkov D, Cowie RJ, Thornton AT, Espinoza HA, McEvoy RD. Pulmonary hypertension and hypoxemia in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 1994;149:416-22
- 104) Leech JA, Onal E, Baer P, Lopata M. Determinants of hypercapnea in occlusive sleep apnea syndrome. *Chest* 1987;92:807-13.
- 105) Maloney MA, Ward SL, Su JA, Durazo-Arvizu RA, Breunig JM, Okpara DU, Gillett ES. Prevalence of pulmonary hypertension on echocardiogram in children with severe obstructive sleep apnea. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2022 Jun 1;18(6):1629-37.
- 106) Weitzenblum E, Krieger J, Apprill M, Vallee E, Ehrhart M, Ratomaharo J, et al. Daytime pulmonary hypertension in patients with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1988;138:345-9.
- 107) Divo M, Celli BR. Multimorbidity in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Clinics in chest medicine*. 2020 Sep 1;41(3):405-19.
- 108) Pantazopoulos I, Daniil Z, Moylan M, Gourgoulianis K, Chalkias A, Zakynthinos S, Ischaki E. Nasal high flow use in COPD patients with hypercapnic respiratory failure: treatment algorithm & review of the literature. *COPD: Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease*. 2020 Jan 2;17(1):101-11.
- 109) Li SQ, Sun XW, Zhang L, Ding YJ, Li HP, Yan YR, Lin YN, Zhou JP, Li QY. Impact of insomnia and obstructive sleep apnea on the risk of acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*. 2021 Aug 1;58:101444.
- 110) Sanders MH, Newman AB, Haggerty CL, Redline S, Lebowitz M, Samet J, et al. Sleep and sleep disordered breathing in adults with predominantly

- 111) Dredla BK, Castillo PR. Cardiovascular consequences of obstructive sleep apnea. *Current cardiology reports*. 2019 Nov;21:1-7.
- 112) Misialek JR, Full KM, Polanka BM, Lakshminarayan K, Gottesman RF, Himali JJ, Pase MP, Lutsey PL. Abstract MP45: Nocturnal Hypoxemia, Obstructive Sleep Apnea and the Risk of Cardiovascular Diseases and Mortality: Insights From the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Participants of the Sleep Heart Health Study. *Circulation*. 2023 Feb 28;147(Suppl_1):AMP45-.
- 113) Peker Y, Hedner J, Norum J, Kraiczi H, Carlson J. Increased incidence of cardiovascular disease in middle aged men with obstructive sleep apnea: a 7 year followup. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2002;166:159-65.
- 114) Hoffstein V, Mateika S. Cardiac arrhythmias, snoring and sleep apnea. *Chest* 1994;106:466-71.
- 115) Xie JY, Liu WX, Ji L, Chen Z, Gao JM, Chen W, Chen GF, Zhu Q. Relationship between inflammatory factors and arrhythmia and heart rate variability in OSAS patients. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*. 2020 Feb 1;24(4):2037-53.
- 116) Flemons WW, Remmers JE, Gillis AM. Sleep apnea and cardiac arrhythmias: is there a relationship? *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1993;148:618-21.
- 117) Catalan-Serra P, Campos-Rodriguez F, Reyes-Nuñez N, Selma-Ferrer MJ, Navarro-Soriano C, Ballester-Canelles M, Soler-Cataluña JJ, Roman-Sanchez P, Almeida-Gonzalez CV, Martinez-Garcia MA. Increased incidence of stroke, but not coronary heart disease, in elderly patients with sleep apnea: role of continuous positive airway pressure treatment. *Stroke*. 2019 Feb;50(2):491-4.
- 118) da Silva Paulitsch F, Zhang L. Continuous positive airway pressure for adults with obstructive sleep apnea and cardiovascular disease: a meta-analysis of randomized trials. *Sleep Medicine*. 2019 Feb 1;54:28-34.
- 119) Lee WJ, Jung KH, Nam HW, Lee YS. Effect of obstructive sleep apnea on cerebrovascular compliance and cerebral small vessel disease. *Plos one*. 2021 Nov 12;16(11):e0259469.
- 120) Mitra AK, Bhuiyan AR, Jones EA. Association and risk factors for obstructive sleep apnea and cardiovascular diseases: a systematic review. *Diseases*. 2021 Dec;9(4):88.
- 121) Titova OE, Yuan S, Baron JA, Lindberg E, Michaëlsson K, Larsson SC. Self-reported symptoms of sleep-disordered breathing and risk of cardiovascular diseases: Observational and Mendelian randomization findings. *Journal of Sleep Research*. 2022 Dec;31(6):e13681.
- 122) Pollicina I, Maniaci A, Lechien JR, Iannella G, Vicini C, Cammaroto G, Cannavici A, Magliulo G, Pace A, Cocuzza S, Di Luca M. Neurocognitive performance improvement after obstructive sleep apnea treatment: state of the art. *Behavioral sciences*. 2021 Dec;11(12):180.
- 123) Zhou L, Liu G, Luo H, Li H, Peng Y, Zong D, Ouyang R. Aberrant hippocampal network connectivity is associated with neurocognitive dysfunction in patients with moderate and severe obstructive sleep apnea. *Frontiers in neurology*. 2020 Dec 11;11:580408.
- 124) Kim HC, Young T, Mathews CG, Weber SM, Woodward AR, Palta M. Sleep disordered breathing and neuropsychological deficits. A population based study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 1997;156:1813-9.
- 125) Tauman R, Gozal D. Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in children. *Expert Rev. Respir. Med*. 2011;5(3):425-40.
- 126) Marcus CL, Brooks LJ, Draper KA, Gozal D, Halbower AC, Jones J, et al. Diagnosis and management of childhood obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Pediatrics*. 2012;130:e714-755.

- 127) Marcus CL, Moore RH, Rosen CL, Giordani B, Garetz SL, Taylor HG, et al. A randomized trial of adenotonsillectomy for childhood sleep apnea. *N Engl J Med.* 2013;368:2366- 2376.
- 128) Venekamp RP, Hearne BJ, Chandrasekharan D, Blackshaw H, Lim J, Schilder AG. Tonsillectomy or adenotonsillectomy versus non-surgical management for obstructive sleepdisordered breathing in children. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2015;10:CD011165.
- 129) De Luca Canto G, Pacheco-Pereira C, Aydinov S, Bhattacharjee R, Tan HL, Kheirandish-Gozal L, et al. Adenotonsillectomy complications: A meta-analysis. *Pediatrics.* 2015;136:702-718.
- 130) Tseng PH, Lee PL, Hsu WC, et al. A higher proportion of metabolic syndrome in Chinese subjects with sleep-disordered breathing: a case-control study based on electrocardiogramderived sleep analysis. *PLoS One.* 2017;12:e0169394.
- 131) Baldassari CM, Lam DJ, Ishman SL, et al. Expert consensus statement: pediatric drug-induced sleep endoscopy. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2021 Jan 05;194599820985000:1e14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0194599820985000>.
- 132) Marcus CL, Brooks LJ, Draper KA, et al. Diagnosis and management of childhood obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Pediatrics.* 2012;130. e714e755.
- 133) Parmar A, Baker A, Narang I. Positive airway pressure in pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Paediatric Respiratory Reviews.* 2019 Aug 1;31:43-51.
- 134) Kennedy B, Lasserson TJ, Wozniak DR, Smith I. Pressure modification or humidification for improving usage of continuous positive airway pressure machines in adults with obstructive sleep apnoea. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews.* 2019(12).
- 135) Ghadiri M, Grunstein RR. Clinical side effects of continuous positive airway pressure in patients with obstructive sleep apnoea. *Respirology.* 2020 Jun;25(6):593-602.
- 136) Levert D, Maniaci J, Tapia IE, Xanthopoulos MS. An overview and application of evidence-based interventions to improve adherence to positive airway pressure for the treatment of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Clinical Practice in Pediatric Psychology.* 2022 Dec;10(4):384.
- 137) Watach AJ, Xanthopoulos MS, Afolabi-Brown O, Saconi B, Fox KA, Qiu M, Sawyer AM. Positive airway pressure adherence in pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: a systematic scoping review. *Sleep medicine reviews.* 2020 Jun 1;51:101273.
- 138) Katz SL, Kirk VG, MacLean JE, Bendiak GN, Harrison MA, Barrowman N, Hoey L, Horwood L, Hadjiyannakis S, Legault L, Foster BJ. Factors related to positive airway pressure therapy adherence in children with obesity and sleep-disordered breathing. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine.* 2020 May 15;16(5):733-41.
- 139) Akkari M, Marianowski R, Chalumeau F, et al. French Society of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery (SFORL) guidelines concerning the role of otorhinolaryngologists in the management of paediatric obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome: follow-up protocol for treated children. *Eur Ann Otorhinolaryngol Head Neck Dis.* 2018;135:427e431.
- 140) Roberts SD, Kapadia H, Greenlee G, Chen ML. Midfacial and dental changes associated with nasal positive airway pressure in children with obstructive sleep apnea and craniofacial conditions. *J Clin Sleep Med.* 2016;12:469e475.
- 141) Sleep cooperative group, respiratory Group, Chinese Pediatrics Society, editorial Board of The Chinese Journal of Practical Pediatrics. Expert consensus on noninvasive positive pressure ventilation in the treatment of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome in children (draft). *Chin J Appl Clin Pediatr.* 2016; 31(19):1451e1455.

- 142) Marcus CL, Beck SE, Traylor J, et al. Randomized, double-blind clinical trial of two different modes of positive airway pressure therapy on adherence and efficacy in children. *J Clin Sleep Med*. 2012;8:37e42.
- 143) Dzierzewski JM, Wallace DM, Wohlgenuth WK. Adherence to continuous positive airway pressure in existing users: self-efficacy enhances the association between continuous positive airway pressure and adherence. *J Clin Sleep Med*. 2016;12: 169e176.
- 144) Rotenberg BW, Murariu D, Pang KP. Trends in CPAP adherence over twenty years of data collection: a flattened curve. *J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2016;45:43.
- 145) Krakow BJ, Obando JJ, Ulibarri VA, McIver ND. Positive airway pressure adherence and subthreshold adherence in posttraumatic stress disorder patients with comorbid sleep apnea. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 2017;11:1923e1932.
- 146) Weaver TE, Sawyer AM. Adherence to continuous positive airway pressure treatment for obstructive sleep apnoea: implications for future interventions. *Indian J Med Res*. 2010;131: 245e258.
- 147) Yang Wei, Zheng li, Xu Zhifei. Long-term follow-up study on non-invasive ventilation in children with moderate to severe obstructive sleep apnea- hypopnea syndrome. *J Otolaryngol Ophthalmol Shangdong Univ*. 2018;32(2):19e24.
- 148) Tsaoussoglou M, Hatzinikolaou S, Baltatzis GE, et al. Expression of leukotriene biosynthetic enzymes in tonsillar tissue of children with obstructive sleep apnea: a prospective nonrandomized study. *JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2014; 140:944e950.
- 149) Liming BJ, Ryan M, Mack D, Ahmad I, Camacho M. Montelukast and nasal corticosteroids to treat pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery*. 2019 Apr;160(4):594-602.
- 150) Aishah A, Loffler KA, Toson B, Mukherjee S, Adams RJ, Altree TJ, Ainge-Allen HW, Yee BJ, Grunstein RR, Carberry JC, Eckert DJ. One month dosing of atomoxetine plus oxybutynin in obstructive sleep apnea: a randomized, placebo-controlled trial. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*. 2023 Apr;20(4):584-95.
- 151) Liming BJ, Ryan M, Mack D, Ahmad I, Camacho M. Montelukast and nasal corticosteroids to treat pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2019;160:594e602.
- 152) Pateron B, Marianowski R, Monteyrol PJ, et al. French Society of ENT (SFORL) guidelines (short version) on the roles of the various treatment options in childhood obstructive sleep apnea-hypopnea syndrome. *Eur Ann Otorhinolaryngol Head Neck Dis*. 2018;135:265e268.
- 153) Ignatiuk D, Schaer B, McGinley B. High flow nasal cannula treatment for obstructive sleep apnea in infants and young children. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2020 Oct;55(10):2791-8.
- 154) Yu JL, Afolabi-Brown O. Updates on management of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Pediatric Investigation*. 2019 Dec 1;3(04):228-35.
- 155) Moore CP. Quantifying and Correlating the Positive Airway Pressure and Upper Airway Gas Clearance During High Flow Nasal Cannula Therapy in Adults.
- 156) Gay P, Lankford A, Diesem R, Richard R. A comparison of two nasal expiratory PAP devices for the treatment of OSA. *Chest*. 2019 Oct 1;156(4):A1063-4.
- 157) Noah WH, Chafin C, Hete B. Suggesting a Diminished Role for Inspiratory Pressure in Treating Uncomplicated Obstructive Sleep Apnea.

- 158) Masoud AI, Alwadei AH, Gowharji LF, Park CG, Carley DW. Relating three-dimensional airway measurements to the apnea-hypopnea index in pediatric sleep apnea patients. *Orthodontics & Craniofacial Research*. 2021 Feb;24(1):137-46.
- 159) Sands SA, Edwards BA, Terrill PI, Butler JP, Owens RL, TarantoMontemurro L, et al. Identifying obstructive sleep apnoea patients responsive to supplemental oxygen therapy. *Eur Respir J*. (2018) 52:1800674. doi: 10.1183/13993003.00674-2018
- 160) O'Donnell C, Crilly S, O'Mahony A, O'Riordan B, Traynor M, Gitau R, McDonald K, Ledwidge MT, O'Shea D, Murphy DJ, Dodd JD. Continuous positive airway pressure but not Liraglutide-mediated weight loss improves early cardiovascular disease in obstructive sleep apnea: Data from a randomized proof-of-concept study. *medRxiv*. 2023:2023-05.
- 161) Zeineddine S, Rowley JA, Chowdhuri S. Oxygen therapy in sleep-disordered breathing. *Chest*. 2021 Aug 1;160(2):701-17.
- 162) Das P, Kashyap R, Kotagal S. Impact of supplemental oxygen on obstructive sleep apnea of infants. *Children (Basel)*. 2018;5:pii: E34.
- 163) Marcus CL, Carroll JL, Bamford O, Pyzik P, Loughlin GM. Supplemental oxygen during sleep in children with sleep-disordered breathing. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 1995;152:1297-1301.
- 164) Aljadeff G, Gozal D, Bailey-Wahl SL, Burrell B, Keens TG, Ward SL. Effects of overnight supplemental oxygen in obstructive sleep apnea in children. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 1996;153:51-55.
- 165) Marcus CL. Sleep-disordered breathing in children. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2001;164:16-30.
- 166) Hales CM, Fryar CD, Carroll MD, Freedman DS, Ogden CL. Trends in obesity and severe obesity prevalence in US youth and adults by sex and age, 2007-2008 to 2015-2016. *JAMA*. 2018;319:1723-1725.
- 167) Marcus CL, Moore RH, Rosen CL, Giordani B, Garetz SL, Taylor HG, et al. A randomized trial of adenotonsillectomy for childhood sleep apnea. *N Engl J Med*. 2013;368:2366- 2376.
- 168) Chan DK, Jan TA, Koltai PJ. Effect of obesity and medical comorbidities on outcomes after adjunct surgery for obstructive sleep apnea in cases of adenotonsillectomy failure. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2012;138:891- 896.
- 169) Verhulst SL, Franckx H, Van Gaal L, De Backer W, Desager K. The effect of weight loss on sleep-disordered breathing in obese teenagers. *Obesity*. 2009;17:1178-1183.
- 170) Amin R, Simakajornboon N, Szczesniak R, Inge T. Early improvement in obstructive sleep apnea and increase in orexin levels after bariatric surgery in adolescents and young adults. *Surg Obes Relat Dis*. 2017;13:95-100
- 171) Pratt JS, Lenders CM, Dionne EA, Hoppin AG, Hsu GL, Inge TH, et al. Best practice updates for pediatric/adolescent weight loss surgery. *Obesity*. 2009;17:901-910.
- 172) Michalsky M, Reichard K, Inge T, Pratt J, Lenders C, American Society for Metabolic and Bariatric Surgery. ASMBS pediatric committee best practice guidelines. *Surg Obes Relat Dis*. 2012;8:1-7.
- 173) Hilmisson H, Lange N, Magnusdottir S. Objective sleep quality and metabolic risk in healthy weight children results from the randomized Childhood Adenotonsillectomy Trial (CHAT). *Sleep and Breathing*. 2019 Dec;23:1197-208.
- 174) Yu JL, Afolabi-Brown O. Updates on management of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Pediatric Investigation*. 2019 Dec 1;3(04):228-35.

- 175) Garg RK, Afifi AM, Garland CB, Sanchez R, Mount DL. Pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: Consensus, controversy, and craniofacial considerations. *Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2017;140:987-997.
- 176) Noller MW, Guilleminault C, Gouveia CJ, Mack D, Neighbors CL, Zaghi S, et al. Mandibular advancement for pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Craniomaxillofac Surg.* 2018;46:1296-1302.
- 177) Lima Illescas MV, Aucapiña Aguilar DC, Vallejo Ledesma LP. A review on the influence of rapid maxillary expansion and mandibular advancement for treating obstructive sleep apnea in children. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry.* 2023 Jan 1;47(1).
- 178) Yang R, Swanson JW, Cielo CM. Craniofacial Syndromes. *Pediatric Sleep Medicine: Mechanisms and Comprehensive Guide to Clinical Evaluation and Management.* 2021:655-65.
- 179) Bitners AC, Arens R. Evaluation and management of children with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Lung.* 2020 Apr;198(2):257-70.
- 180) Pirelli P, Saponara M, Guilleminault C. Rapid maxillary expansion (RME) for pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: a 12-year follow-up. *Sleep Med.* 2015;16:933-935
- 181) Pirelli P, Saponara M, Guilleminault C. Rapid maxillary expansion in children with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. *Sleep.* 2004;27:761-766.
- 182) Lee CF, Lee CH, Hsueh WY, Lin MT, Kang KT. Prevalence of obstructive sleep apnea in children with Down syndrome: A meta-analysis. *J Clin Sleep Med.* 2018;14:867-875.
- 183) Best J, Mutchnick S, Ida J, Billings KR. Trends in management of obstructive sleep apnea in pediatric patients with Down syndrome. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol.* 2018;110:1-5.
- 184) Cielo CM, Duffy KA, Taylor JA, Marcus CL, Kalish JM. Obstructive Sleep Apnea in Children With BeckwithWiedemann Syndrome. *J Clin Sleep Med.* 2019;15:375-381.
- 185) Kang KT, Koltai PJ, Lee CH, Lin MT, Hsu WC. Lingual tonsillectomy for treatment of pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: A meta-analysis. *JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2017;143:561-568.
- 186) Camacho M, Noller MW, Zaghi S, Reckley LK, FernandezSalvador C, Ho E, et al. Tongue surgeries for pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: a systematic review and metaanalysis. *Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol.* 2017;274:2981-2990.
- 187) Thorne MC, Garetz SL. Laryngomalacia: review and summary of current clinical practice in 2015. *Paediatr Respir Rev.* 2016;17:3-8
- 188) Bedwell J, Zalzal G. Laryngomalacia. *Semin Pediatr Surg.* 2016;25:119-122.
- 189) Camacho M, Dunn B, Torre C, Sasaki J, Gonzales R, Liu SY, et al. Supraglottoplasty for laryngomalacia with obstructive sleep apnea: A systematic review and metaanalysis. *Laryngoscope.* 2016;126:1246-1255
- 190) Guilleminault C, Simmons FB, Motta J, Cumiskey J, Rosekind M, Schroeder JS, et al. Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome and tracheostomy. Long-term follow-up experience. *Arch Intern Med.* 1981;141:985-988.
- 191) Rizzi CJ, Amin JD, Isaiah A, Valdez TA, Jeyakumar A, Smart SE, et al. Tracheostomy for severe pediatric obstructive sleep apnea: Indications and outcomes. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2017;157:309-313.
- 192) Roland PS, Rosenfeld RM, Brooks LJ, Friedman NR, Jones J, Kim TW, et al. Clinical practice guideline: Polysomnography for sleep-disordered breathing prior to tonsillectomy in children. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2011;145 (1 Suppl):S1-15.

- 193) Van den Bossche K, Van de Perck E, Wellman A, Kazemeini E, Willemen M, Verbraecken J, Vanderveken OM, Vena D, Op de Beeck S. Comparison of drug-induced sleep endoscopy and natural sleep endoscopy in the assessment of upper airway pathophysiology during sleep: protocol and study design. *Frontiers in Neurology*. 2021 Dec 7;12:768973.
- 194) Vroegop AV, Vanderveken OM, Verbraecken JA. Drug-induced sleep endoscopy: evaluation of a selection tool for treatment modalities for obstructive sleep apnea. *Respiration*. 2020;99(5):451-7.
- 195) Manickam PV, Shott SR, Boss EF, Cohen AP, Meinzen-Derr JK, Amin RS, et al. Systematic review of site of obstruction identification and non-CPAP treatment options for children with persistent pediatric obstructive sleep apnea. *Laryngoscope*. 2016;126:491-500.
- 196) Donnelly LF, Casper KA, Chen B, Koch BL. Defining normal upper airway motion in asymptomatic children during sleep by means of cine MR techniques. *Radiology*. 2002;223:176-180.
- 197) Shott SR, Donnelly LF. Cine magnetic resonance imaging: evaluation of persistent airway obstruction after tonsil and adenoidectomy in children with Down syndrome. *Laryngoscope*. 2004;114:1724-1729.
- 198) Fricke BL, Donnelly LF, Shott SR, Kalra M, Poe SA, Chini BA, et al. Comparison of lingual tonsil size as depicted on MR imaging between children with obstructive sleep apnea despite previous tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy and normal controls. *Pediatr Radiol*. 2006;36:518-523.
- 199) Isaiah A, Kiss E, Olomu P, Koral K, Mitchell RB. Characterization of upper airway obstruction using cine MRI in children with residual obstructive sleep apnea after adenotonsillectomy. *Sleep Med*. 2018;50:79-86.
- 200) Isaiah A, Kiss E, Olomu P, Koral K, Mitchell RB. Characterization of upper airway obstruction using cine MRI in children with residual obstructive sleep apnea after adenotonsillectomy. *Sleep Med*. 2018;50:79-86
- 201) Strollo PJ, Jr., Soose RJ, Maurer JT, de Vries N, Cornelius J, Froymovich O, et al. Upper-airway stimulation for obstructive sleep apnea. *N Engl J Med*. 2014;370:139-149
- 202) Caloway CL, Diercks GR, Keamy D, de Guzman V, Soose R, Raol N, et al. Update on hypoglossal nerve stimulation in children with down syndrome and obstructive sleep apnea. *Laryngoscope*. 2019;doi:10.1002/lary.28138. (Epub ahead of print)
- 203) Bamford NJ, Potter SJ, Baskerville CL, Harris PA, Bailey SR. Influence of dietary restriction and low-intensity exercise on weight loss and insulin sensitivity in obese equids. *Journal of veterinary internal medicine*. 2019 Jan;33(1):280-6.
- 204) Silva de Sousa A, Pereira da Rocha A, Brandão Tavares DR, Frazão Okazaki JÉ, de Andrade Santana MV, Fernandes Moça Trevisani V, Pereira Nunes Pinto AC. Respiratory muscle training for obstructive sleep apnea: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Sleep Research*..e13941.